

RECEPTION & OBSTRUCTION: THE ROLE OF INDIRECT TRANSLATION IN UNDERSTANDING AND MISUNDERSTANDING THE THOUGHT OF EVAGRIUS PONTICUS

Tomás Vicente Ferreira,

International Association of Paremiology
(Secretary of the General Assembly)
Yerevan State University (graduate student)

Alda Vicente,

International Association of Paremiology (member)
Email: tferreira2@campus.ul.pt
Email: tvicenteferreira1@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19333451>

Keywords: *Evagrius Ponticus - Origenism – Armenian – Syriac – Indirect Translation*

The posthumous reputation of the great 4th century ascetic theologian and learned monk Evagrius Ponticus has been undeservedly tarnished since the reign of Emperor Justinian, when he was the target of equivocal, posthumous and quite irregular condemnations more than a hundred and fifty years after his death in the peace of the Church in January of 399 AD. Though in later centuries he was associated to the neo-Origenist party embroiled in the first of the Origenist controversies, his name never really occurs in the context of that controversy in the pen of his contemporaries, as Gabriel Bunge has highlighted in several of his copious and masterful writings on Evagrius. Furthermore, he was highly respected and admired during his lifetime by the greatest minds among his contemporaries, and for a century and a half after he died, only becoming seriously suspect (through a process of absolutely unfounded transmogrification) under the aegis of the sublimely heavy-handed Justinian and his court theologians, who quite preposterously had his *person* (as opposed to just some of his thesis) condemned *post mortem* on the sidelines and aftermath of the Fifth Ecumenical Council in 553-554, together with other figures of the theological past, such as Dydimus the Blind, who were not palatable to who was "calling the shots" in 553.

Since then, a conspicuously thick fog of suspicion and obfuscation has lain upon the person, the teachings and the works of Evagrius, whose name has been repeatedly hammered as heretical or heterodox together with the names of Dydimus, Origen and other outstanding theologians of the early centuries who fell foul of the censorship of later orthodoxies of theological thought in the 6th century. The clearing of that thick fog has not been helped by the fact that one of the pioneers of Evagrian studies in the 20th century, Antoine Guillaumont, and his continuators, was also in effect a detractor of his subject of study who quite unaccountably shared the traditional hostility to Evagrius common to many an unhealthy theological environment over the last fifteen centuries (and also common to healthier ones, alas!). This is to such an extent that one would be forgiven for thinking the pro-Evagrian case to have been fully proven by the simple thunderous passion with which so many thinkers, and so many *unthinking*, desire to prove the most preposterous smears on his theological thoughts and/or to boycott any attempt at rehabilitating his reputation or even merely at re-examining the evidence of his dossier.

Paradoxically, unlike Origen, whose works, despite the growing animosity of established theological orthodoxies over the centuries, have largely survived in the original Greek text, a very big portion of Evagrius's works only survive in Armenian or Syriac translations, the

original Greek text having been all but completely lost, very possibly as a consequence of his maladroit condemnation in 553-554. (It is interesting to notice that, whereas the Greek religious *oikumene* to which he belonged disavowed him to a large extent and tarnished his reputation or allowed it to be tarnished, Evagrius remained always highly regarded in the context of the Armenian Christianity, and in fact the Armenian Apostolic and Syriac Orthodox Churches are alone in according him a deserved reverence, venerating him as a saint, with a feast day on 11 February in the Armenian liturgical calendar..)

Granted that for centuries it has often been difficult to pierce the dark fog to interpret or reconstruct his thought accurately, in this paper we will try to focus on how the fact that some of his most important and most contentious writings survive only in Armenian and Syriac translations, and thus the fact that modern scholars and exegetes of his thought must rely solely on those translations for knowledge a lot of what he wrote – which amounts to saying that a modern scholar of Evagrius often finds himself in the position of an *indirect translator*, i.e., someone interpreting, editing and translating a text on the basis of a translation whose confrontation with the original is impossible – has functioned as hindrance to modern scholarship in most attempts at accurately assessing the contents of the theological teaching of Evagrius Ponticus. The translations of his texts into Armenian and Syriac in late antiquity have saved from oblivion a lot of his writing that the Greek world from Justinian onwards consigned to destruction, serving in a way as a kind of “pivot languages”, and in so doing those translations allow us to try to clear the view to reassess and reassemble his ideas in an accurate and clear light. But would it be the case that those translations also offer us terminological and other linguistic twists, semantic distortions and imprecisions that have may have subtly contributed to hinder even up to the present a rapid, unequivocal and uncontroversial rehabilitation of Evagrius’ memory? And if so, how can one overcome those cruxes to peer behind them into the ghostly palimpsest of what might have been on the original Greek texts?

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